

Star Formation Rates of High Redshift Galaxies: JADES High H α Emitters and their Evolution with Redshift and Luminosity

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ABSTRACT

To understand the formation and evolution of galaxies in our Universe, the star formation rate (SFR) is an important parameter. Here we use deep Near-Infrared Camera (NIRCam) imaging with six medium band filters from JADES (*JWST* Advanced Deep Extragalactic Survey) to form catalogues of high H α -emitting galaxies in the GOODS-S field across a redshift range of $z \sim 1.3$ to $z \sim 4.5$. These catalogues represent the galaxies with high SFRs, as H α serves as a marker of star formation. The filters used—F335M, F300M, F250M, F210M, F182M, and F162M—comprise the medium bands currently with the deepest imaging from the *James Webb Space Telescope (JWST)* with exposure times of over 30 hours. We utilized the JADES photometry to determine the number density, luminosity, and H α equivalent width (EW) values of the high H α emitters across the filters. We see evidence of increased density of high H α emitters in the F250M and F300M filters, corresponding to redshifts $z \sim 2.6$ to $z \sim 3.9$. These filters also show higher luminosities of the high-H α -emitting galaxies when compared to adjacent filters. Additionally, a peak in the rest H α EW is observed in the F182M filter, at an average redshift $z \sim 1.8$. The photometry from JADES enables this analysis of high-H α -emitting galaxies at high redshifts and low luminosities to contribute to the understanding of how the number density and luminosity of vigorously-star-forming galaxies changes with redshift.

1. INTRODUCTION

Young stars dominate stellar UV emission of galaxies. These young stars, being nestled in their birth gas and dust clouds, ionize nearby gas with their emitted UV photons. In particular, only stars with mass greater than $10 M_{\odot}$ and younger than 20 Myr produce ionizing flux detectable at cosmological distances (12). As a result, the photoionization effects of the UV emission provide a measure of the instantaneous, or on at least 20 Myr timescales, star formation rate (SFR) at the period being observed, one that is independent of the galaxy's history.

The ionized hydrogen gas eventually recombines with an electron, and the resulting cascade down the hydrogen energy levels to the $n = 2$ level forms the Balmer series. The $n = 3$ to $n = 2$ transition within this series results in the H α emission line at about 656.3 nm. H α emission lines are often used to determine SFRs as they experience less extinction than the brighter Ly α lines and are more easily observed than emission lines at higher wavelengths. While the [O II] 3727 line is also associated with star formation, it is affected by the gas-phase metallicity (22). The reliability and strength of

the H α emission line serve to make it a good SFR indicator.

Furthermore, the equivalent width (EW) of the emission line is a proxy for the star formation rate per unit stellar mass as it accounts for the baseline intensity of the spectrum. The EW is the width of a rectangle with the height of the continuum, or the average intensity, that has the same area as the spectral line, in this case the H α line. In this way, large H α EW indicate vigorously star-forming galaxies. So the H α line emission can be used to determine SFR and sSFR.

However, observation of the H α emission line was, until recently, limited to lower-redshift galaxies as this nebular emission line shifts into the infrared for redshifts (z) greater than one. The successful launch of the *James Webb Space Telescope (JWST)* enabled looking at this line at high-redshifts which were previously very difficult to observe. Furthermore, JADES, the *JWST* Advanced Deep Extragalactic Survey, collects very deep data in a small field, which is optimal for measuring star formation in less luminous galaxies (JADES; (3)). With the advance in observational abilities, the SFRs for high-redshift galaxies and lower-luminosity galaxies can be determined and compared. Here, we use photom-

etry collected by *JWST*'s NIRCcam instrument with six medium band filters—F335M, F300M, F250M, F210M, F182M, and F162M—to analyze the SFRs of galaxies with redshifts spanning 1.3 to 4.5 (JADES; (3)). The data used are taken over the Great Observatories Origins Deep Survey southern-hemisphere field (GOODS-S; (8)) and include observations through October 2023.

Previous studies suggest an evolution in the rest-frame $EW_0(H\alpha)$ over redshifts zero to eight (5; 19). However, many of these previous studies have had limited sources to analyze due to observational limitations prior to *JWST*, so the addition of many more data points across redshifts would greatly inform this suggested evolution. Additionally, Endsley et al. (2023) have noted an unexpected lack of $EW_0(H\alpha)$ dependence on the UV luminosity of the source galaxy, though they suggest recent changes in star formation histories may be shrouding the expected effect of increasing $EW_0(H\alpha)$ with lower metallicities at fainter UV luminosities. The relationship between luminosity and $EW_0(H\alpha)$ will be further explored using the new data. The primary goals of this paper are to elucidate the relationships between SFR and redshift and SFR and galaxy luminosity.

This paper is organized as follows. First, we will discuss the imaging data and catalogue selection for high $H\alpha$ emitters. Then, we will present the determination of $H\alpha$ line flux, continuum intensity, and photometric redshifts of galaxies within the catalogues. These values will define the luminosity and $EW_0(H\alpha)$. Finally, the number density of high $EW_0(H\alpha)$ galaxies will be compared across redshifts and luminosities. For this paper, a flat Λ CDM cosmology with parameters $h = 0.67$, $\Omega_m = 0.315$, and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.685$ is assumed.

2. IMAGING DATA AND CATALOGUE SELECTION

In this section, we describe the imaging data and analysis to achieve the desired catalogues of high $H\alpha$ -emitters. Then, we will explain the determination of luminosity, $EW_0(H\alpha)$, and the number density of high $H\alpha$ -emitters across redshifts.

2.1. Imaging Data and Filters

Data collected using six NIRCcam filters are used in this paper (17). The filters in question are F335M, F300M, F250M, F210M, F182M, and F162M. These filters span both medium- and wide-band as well as short wavelength channels and long wavelength channels, which are separated by a dichroic in the actual instrument (11). Very deep imaging in these six filters as part of GO program 3215 (4) makes them well suited for

Table 1. Filter Information: The wide band control filter, the average exposure time in the band (in ksec), the comoving volume surveyed for each filter (in Mpc^3), and the redshift range for identified high emitters.

Filter	Wide-band	t_{exp} (ksec)	$V(\text{Mpc}^3)$	z range
F162M	F150W	82.6	2972.7	1.308 – 1.658
F182M	F200W	166.1	4079.0	1.574 – 2.058
F210M	F200W	125.4	4197.3	1.973 – 2.423
F250M	F277W	165.2	3820.9	2.594 – 3.041
F300M	F277W	124.0	6039.8	3.213 – 3.923
F335M	F356W	99.4	6416.3	3.724 – 4.519

measuring star formation rates of less luminous galaxies. Information about the filters and their wide-band comparisons is in Table 1, and their overlap is shown in Figure 1. The flux of each source is determined within a Kron aperture (14) with a Kron (14) factor $k = 1.2$, as this Kron factor value provides the optimal S/N (6). The fluxes are reported in nano-Janskys (nJy). The error of the flux reading is the measured flux uncertainty within the Kron aperture.

As an initial cut of the data, any entries with bad pixels, where there is missing or poor data, or a very low signal-to-noise ratio are removed. In addition, any source with a neighbor greater than ten times brighter or with poor deviation from the background—as determined by the flux ratio from the desired aperture to one with twice the radius—is removed. In this way, clear sources are isolated. In addition, only sources which are also viewed in the F162M or F250M filters are used.

To determine if there is excess flux due to $H\alpha$ emission, the range of redshifts for which the $H\alpha$ line would fall into the selected filter is calculated. For example, for the F335M filter, which has a wavelength range from 3.177 microns to 3.537 microns, the 0.6563 micron $H\alpha$ line would lie at 3.177 microns for a galaxy with a redshift about 3.84 and at 3.537 microns for a galaxy with a redshift about 4.39. So, the range of redshifts for the sources observed with this filter, with an extra three-percent window on either end of the redshift range to account for sources with slightly misidentified photometric redshifts, would be $z = 3.73$ to $z = 4.52$. This same calculation was done for all filters to select for the galaxies whose $H\alpha$ emission line would lie within the selected filter. Across all six filters utilized in this paper, sources with a range of redshifts from 1.3 to 4.5 are analyzed. This range includes the suggested peak in star formation rate density at about $z = 2$ (16), which positions this

study to better understand the evolution of star formation rate.

2.2. Isolating $H\alpha$ Line Emission

Figure 1. NIRCam Filters: The bands for each of the NIRCam filters is shown. In addition, the effect of the dichroic is shown by the grey bar dividing the filters. For this project, only the wide and medium band filters, shown in the two middle rows, are used. Image Credit: JWSTDocs

For a baseline continuum to compare the medium-band fluxes to, we used the nearest adjacent or overlapping wide band (see Figure 1 or Table 1). The photon counts in a filter, provided a top-hat filter response curve and a constant F_ν , are proportional to $F_\nu * \ln(\lambda_{max}/\lambda_{min})$, where the λ_{max} and λ_{min} are the blue and red edges of the filter. So the flux from each filter is essentially weighted by this natural log of its wavelength ratio. These weights can be used to compare filters and, in particular, determine the excess flux density. Withers et al. (21) have demonstrated that *JWST*'s NIRCam medium band photometry can be accurately used to identify extreme emission-line galaxies. They did so by comparing the photometry to the NIRSpec spectroscopy of 15 sources (21). As such, the photometry used here can also identify the high $H\alpha$ -emitting galaxies. Sources with high S/N for the excess flux density were identified as high $H\alpha$ -emitting candidates.

These excess emitters were then selected based on photometric redshift determination so that only those with $H\alpha$ emission within the filter were considered. These photometric redshifts were calculated using EAZY (2). EAZY outputs the z corresponding to the minimum $\chi^2(z)$ for fitting the observed photometry across a redshift grid based on template data. The data and parameters outlined in Hainline et al. (10) are used here (17).

Visual inspection of the photometry, template spectra, and redshift estimates confirmed the selection criteria as isolating strong candidates for high $H\alpha$ -emitters. See Figure 2 for the NIRCam SEDs and photometry for selected samples of each filter. In each graph of template spectra, the medium band filter is elevated in comparison to the wide band, indicating an excess of flux received within the medium band filter.

A map of the high emitters found in each filter (see Figure 3) illustrates the spatial distribution of the excess emitters. In particular, the large overdensities in F250M and F300M and clustering of the high emitters likely due to large scale structure become apparent in these maps.

2.3. Determining the Luminosities and $EW_0(H\alpha)$ s

The luminosity and $EW_0(H\alpha)$ were determined based on a model of what the measured flux from each filter would be given a continuum flux, A , and the excess flux density, l , due to $H\alpha$ emission. The flux density of the source is modeled as

$$F_\nu = A + (l\nu)\delta(\nu - \nu_{line}) \quad (1)$$

so the normalized number of photon counts, F , would be $F = \frac{F_\nu}{F_{ref}}$ where F_{ref} is 1 nJy. This gives the model (20)

$$F_\lambda = \frac{l}{\ln\left(\frac{\lambda_{max}}{\lambda_{min}}\right)} + A \quad (2)$$

With this model and the data for both the medium and wide band filters, the A and l values can be determined for each candidate. The line flux $f = \int F_\nu d\nu$ from the line is $l\nu$. In this case, the line flux is the $H\alpha$ line flux, so the wavelength of the line is the redshifted wavelength of the $H\alpha$ line. The observed EW is the line flux divided by the flux density per wavelength as this would provide the width of a rectangle with the height of the continuum which has an area equivalent to the excess flux. This flux density per wavelength is $F_\lambda = \frac{l}{\lambda} F_{cont}$, where $F_{cont} = A$. So

$$EW_{H\alpha} = \frac{l\nu}{\frac{l\nu}{\lambda}} = \frac{l}{A} \lambda \quad (3)$$

The rest frame $EW(H\alpha)$, $EW_0(H\alpha)$, is the observed $EW(H\alpha)$ divided by $(1+z)$ and converted to Angstroms.

The luminosity is related to the line flux by the relation

$$L = f * 4\pi D_L^2 \quad (4)$$

The luminosity distance is determined by first calculating the proper motion distance, as a flat universe is assumed. This distance is

$$x(z) = \int_0^z \frac{c}{H(z')} dz' \quad (5)$$

Figure 2. Photometry, template spectra, and redshift determination for a sample of high $H\alpha$ -emitter candidates. (a) is a candidate from F335M, (b) from F300M, (c) from F250M, (d) from F210M, (e) from F182M, and (f) from F162M.

An $\omega = -1$ Λ CDM cosmology is assumed with $H_0 = 67$ and $\Omega_m = 0.315$ (Planck Collaboration; (1)). The luminosity distance is this proper motion distance multiplied by $(1+z)$. This distance is used to calculate the luminosity from the line flux, and this value is converted to units of ergs/s.

Calculating the number density of high $H\alpha$ -emitting galaxies determined by each filter requires determining the comoving volume observed by each filter. As the comoving volume interior to a sphere for a flat universe is $\frac{4\pi}{3}x(z)^3$, the comoving volume for an observed solid

angle and between two redshifts is

$$V = \frac{\Omega}{3} [x(z_{\max})^3 - x(z_{\min})^3] \quad (6)$$

Now, the values for $EW_0(H\alpha)$, luminosity, number density, and redshift can be compared.

3. THE EVOLUTION OF SFR WITH REDSHIFT

The SFR is related to the $H\alpha$ emission by a one-parameter scaling law (12). The conversion is (12):

$$\text{SFR}(M_{\odot} \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}) = 7.9 * 10^{-42} * L(H\alpha)(\text{ergs} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}) \quad (7)$$

Figure 3. Locations of the High Emitters: The identified high $H\alpha$ emitters are shown in dark blue while the other observed sources are shown in grey for each filter. The marker size for the high emitters has also been increased compared to the other sources. Each source is plotted at its RA and Dec.

However, this scaling parameter would change with the stellar population assumed, so for this paper the $H\alpha$ emission strength serves as an adequate proxy for SFR. In addition, the number density of high $H\alpha$ -emitters highlights the evolution of SFR across redshift. However, it is notable that due to the large scale structure of the Universe, the number density measured in the specific survey region is not necessarily indicative of the overall number density at that redshift.

The expected results would be a peak in star formation at $z \sim 2$. This would be in accordance with the “cosmic noon” of robust star formation (18). It is estimated that as much as half of today’s observed stellar mass was born in between $z \sim 3$ and $z \sim 1$ (18). So a strong burst of star formation occurring within this range should be indicated by an increase in the number density of star forming galaxies around that time. While there is elevated number density for the middle bands shown, the peak well before the “cosmic noon” and the tapering of the number density may suggest either limitations of this survey or a contradiction of the cosmic noon model. Differences in exposure time, volume surveyed, and the fluctuations in the large-scale structure of the Universe could contribute to this surprising result. The steepness of this peak, however, leaves the question

of why there is no gradual decline even with possible fluctuations due to differences in observation.

If this star formation burst expected at $z \sim 2$ was indeed an abrupt change in the SFR of the galaxy, the luminosity of the galaxy at that time would likely be low due to an absence of young stars prior to the burst. This luminosity, or the baseline flux, thus correlates to the star formation history of the galaxy. The $EW_0(H\alpha)$ is an observational equivalent to the specific star formation rate (sSFR) as it accounts for both the continuum—an approximation for the stellar mass of the galaxy in terms of how luminous it is—and the line flux—the current rate of star formation. Figure 4b shows both an absence of strong specific star formation prior to the cosmic noon and a spike in the sSFR near the end around $z \sim 1.8$. The elevation in $EW_0(H\alpha)$ continues into $z \sim 1.5$ as well. These results do suggest a strong burst of star formation in terms of sSFR around $z \sim 2$. In addition, the sSFR as suggested by the $EW_0(H\alpha)$ increases from $z \sim 2$ to $z \sim 5$, in agreement with results from the Cosmic Assembly Near-infrared Deep Extragalactic Legacy Survey (CANDELS; (9)) photometry (15). The context of a greater range of redshifts shows this dip towards $z \sim 2$ but then a sharp peak in sSFR at $z \sim 1.8$. While some of the variations in Figure 4 are due to changes in the limiting depth of observation at different redshifts,

Figure 4. (a) The number density of high H α -emitters observed with each filter plotted against the average redshift of that filter. (b) The median rest EW (in Angstroms) of each filter plotted against the average redshift of that filter.

these variations do not greatly attenuate the observed sharp peaks.

4. THE RELATIONSHIP OF SFR AND LUMINOSITY

By virtue of the very deep imaging, this set of high emitters includes many low-luminosity galaxies. Figure 5 shows the distribution of the high emitters by luminosity and, equivalently, by SFR. Here it becomes apparent just how faint the sources are. The minimum line flux measured is $\sim 3 \times 10^{-19} \text{ ergs} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. For reference, a previous study for H α emission at a similar redshift reported a minimum line flux of $1 \times 10^{-16} \text{ ergs} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, significantly higher than what was observed here (7). This difference highlights how this survey enables the observation of very faint galaxies.

In addition, Figure 6 shows the distribution of luminosities among the high emitters and across filters more clearly. The F300M and F250M filters again stand out as having an overdensity, and both have a similar distribution of higher luminosity galaxies. These results are most meaningful when compared to F335M, as lower-luminosity galaxies can be probed at lower redshifts due to the flux sensitivity of NIRCcam so F335M would be expected to have the greatest skew towards higher luminosities. To counteract some of this skew, Figure 6c and d show the same plots for galaxies with a minimum $\text{EW}_0(\text{H}\alpha)$ for all filters. In addition to the increased densities and luminosities in F300M and F250M, the more even distribution in luminosities in F162M compared to the other filters is also highlighted. This suggests a wider range of galaxy types, in terms of luminosity, with elevated H α emission.

The $\text{EW}_0(\text{H}\alpha)$ plotted against the log of the luminosity in Figure 7 demonstrates the expectation that lower-luminosity galaxies can be probed at lower redshifts as overall the plots shift towards lower luminosities along with redshift. As the narrowest filter is the F250M, it can probe the lowest $\text{EW}_0(\text{H}\alpha)$ values. Figure 1 shows the differences in filter width. For all filters, there seems to be an elongated tail from a normal Gaussian distribution towards higher luminosities. This skew is likely due to the flux limit of observation; there is a cutoff for the lowest luminosity observable in each filter.

5. SUMMARY

We used deep NIRCcam imaging with six medium band filters from JADES to form catalogues of high H α -emitting galaxies in the GOODS-S field across a redshift range of $z \sim 1.3$ to $z \sim 4.5$. The photometry from JADES enabled the analysis of high-H α -emitting galaxies at high redshifts and low luminosities. We found evidence of increased density of high H α emitters in the F250M and F300M filters, corresponding to redshifts $z \sim 2.6$ to $z \sim 3.9$. The F300M filter also shows elevated luminosities of the high-H α -emitting galaxies (see Figure 6d). The F162M filter exhibits a more even distribution of high-H α -emitting galaxies across luminosities. Additionally, a peak in the H α EW_0 is observed in the F182M filter, at an average redshift $z \sim 1.8$. These results show disagreement with a model of a “cosmic noon” in which a peak in SFR occurs around $z \sim 2$. We observe this peak as an increase in SFR from $z \sim 4$ to $z \sim 3$ with a steep drop-off towards $z \sim 2$. However, the results do suggest a peak in sSFR, based on $\text{EW}_0(\text{H}\alpha)$, at $z \sim 2$. Again, this peak is quite steep and the el-

Figure 5. Luminosity and SFR Distribution in Each Filter: The luminosity (and related SFR) distribution of the identified high emitters in each filter.

evaluation in sSFR continues into $z \sim 1.5$. Overall, the results suggest a need to reexamine the idea of a cosmic noon and to consider the effects of large scale structure on this survey as the observed overdensities may be a result of this structure. Of note, the overdensities were observed in two filters across a large range in redshift of almost 1.5, suggesting they may not be just an artifact of large scale structure. The advanced capabilities of *JWST* enabled this study of the SFRs of high redshift and low luminosity galaxies which were previously difficult to survey due to observational limitations. *JWST* will continue to contribute to the understanding of the star formation evolution of galaxies across redshifts and luminosities, and the questions elicited by the results

here will be better understood in the context of more JADES data.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I am very grateful to my advisor Professor Daniel Eisenstein for all of his guidance and assistance with this project. I greatly appreciate this opportunity to work with such exciting data from JADES and to learn so much about astrophysics research. I also want to thank my reviewer Dr. Matthew Ashby for his helpful comments. Finally, I would like to express my gratitude for Dr. Xingang Chen and my AY 98 classmates for all of their support and advice along the way. Thank you to everyone who made this project possible.

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Figure 6. (a) Log of the number of high $H\alpha$ -emitters with a luminosity above the lowest luminosity value for emitters identified in that filter plotted against the log of the luminosity for each of those emitters. All filters are plotted together. (b) Log of the number density of high $H\alpha$ -emitters with a luminosity above the lowest luminosity value for emitters identified in that filter plotted against the log of the luminosity for each of those emitters. The number density is determined from the number (see (a)) divided by the volume surveyed. All filters are plotted together. (c) Given a EW floor of 300 Angstroms, log of the number of high $H\alpha$ -emitters with a luminosity above the lowest luminosity value for emitters identified in that filter plotted against the log of the luminosity for each of those emitters. All filters are plotted together. (d) Given a EW floor of 300 Angstroms, log of the number density of high $H\alpha$ -emitters with a luminosity above the lowest luminosity value for emitters identified in that filter plotted against the log of the luminosity for each of those emitters. The number density is determined from the number (see (c)) divided by the volume surveyed. All filters are plotted together.

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Figure 7. The rest EW plotted against the log of the luminosity. The luminosity is in units of ergs/s and the EW in Angstroms. Axes are held constant to clarify the differences across filters. The error bars are the error of the EW propagated from the initial photon count errors.

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